

Influence of fibre/matrix interactions on the
damage tolerance behaviour of composites

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ABSTRACT

An experimental test series indicated considerably lower strain energy release rates in case of poor adhesion. This feature was observed for both a peel (mode I, WTDCB-specimen) and a shear (mode II, ENF-specimen) loading mode.

In a qualitative evaluation on damage tolerance it is shown that fibre/matrix debonding, being the cause of low interlaminar fracture toughness, can result in improved composite damage tolerance. The main reasons for this beneficial influence are:

- decreasing stress concentration in debonded fibres
- possible occurrence of "secondary" energy dissipating mechanisms like fibre pull-out

The advantageous effect of fibre/matrix debonding on damage tolerance can be expected for tension loaded (static or fatigue) specimens with an (artificial) damage and for general impact conditions. The debonding will generally be disadvantageous for compression loaded specimens.

1: INTRODUCTION

Since the early days of aircraft it was recognized that weight is never a stimulan for getting off the ground. Therefore reducing weight was (and still is) one of the important driving forces in the search for and the evaluation of new, often expensive materials.

Although the potential weight savings of composites (up to 40% compared to aluminium) have been recognized for some ten years, only recently important breakthroughs did appear in the usage of composite materials for primary structures in the civil aircraft industry (vertical tailplane A320).

One of the remaining problem areas for the structural use of composites, and most probably the most important obstacle to achieve the potential weight savings, is the limited damage tolerance of these materials. In this paper, attention is focussed on damage tolerance and more specifically, on the possible influence of fibre/matrix adhesion on this

phenomenon. In chapter 2, the results of an experimental test series are presented concerning the effect of fibre/matrix adhesion on interlaminar fracture toughness. Chapter 3 starts with an introductory survey on the possible influence of the matrix on the damage tolerance of composites (section 3.1). In section 3.2, a qualitative evaluation is presented linking fibre/matrix adhesion and interlaminar fracture toughness with the damage tolerance behaviour of composites.

2: EFFECT OF FIBRE/MATRIX ADHESION ON THE INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

In this chapter the test results are presented of an investigation performed on the influence of fibre/matrix adhesion on the interlaminar fracture toughness. This investigation was part of a larger test series on the characterisation and evaluation of fibre/matrix adhesion (ref.1). Different fibre/matrix adhesion levels have been attained by embedding three types of fibres (aramid, glass and carbon) in an identical toughened epoxy adhesive. Two specimen types have been selected for the test series:

- 1) width tapered double cantilever beam (WTDCB-) specimen

The double cantilever beam specimen, intensively used to characterize the mode I (peel) fracture behaviour of adhesives or laminates, consists of two (metal) adherends bonded together by an intermediate layer (fig.1).

Fig. 1: width tapered double cantilever beam specimen

In this test series, a specimen configuration (width tapered) has been selected for which the strain energy release rate (G_{IC}) is solely a function of the critical load level:

$$G_{IC} = P_{cr}^2 \cdot Q \quad (\text{N/m})$$

where $Q = (1/2b_a) \cdot (dC/da) = \text{constant}$
 P_{cr} : critical load level (N)
 b_a : width of specimen at crack
length "a" (m)
a: crack length (m)
C: compliance of the specimen (m^2/N)

2) end-notched flexure (ENF-) specimen

The ENF-specimen, used for the characterization of a mode II (shear) fracture behaviour, consists of two (metal) adherends bonded together by an intermediate layer (fig.2). The specimen is tested on a three-point bending fixture.

Fig. 2: End-notched flexure specimen

The following relation is valid for the strain energy release rate (G_{IIC}) of the ENF-specimen:

$$G_{IIC} = (3P_{CR}^2 a^2)/(8EbI) \quad (N/m)$$

where P_{CR} : critical load level (N)
a: crack length (m)
E: Young's modulus specimen (N/m^2)
I: moment of inertia (m^4)
b: width of the specimen (m)

These two specimen types have been selected because:

1) The data obtained are considered as being representative for the interlaminar fracture toughness of composites in real structures; the WTDCB-specimen for a mode I (peel), the ENF-specimen for a mode II (shear) loading.

2) These specimen configurations allow the evaluation of the effect of fibre/matrix adhesion on interlaminar fracture toughness, independent of other fibre properties.

The results of the test series are presented in fig.3 (static test series, 3 to 6 specimens per variable). For reference also the data for the adhesive (no embedded fibres) are added in fig.3. The following remarks can be made:

Fig. 3: The strain energy release rate of four intermediate layers

1) The strain energy release rate of an aramid prepreg is, both for a peel (G_{IC}) and a shear (G_{IIc}) mode, low compared to a glass and carbon prepreg. Microscopic examination of the fracture surfaces of the aramid prepreg showed completely smooth aramid fibres (fig.4) which points to relatively poor adhesion and, as a result, low G_{IC} and G_{IIc} values. The carbon and glass surfaces are, after fracture, still covered with the matrix material (fig.5).

Fig. 4: Fracture surface of an aramid fibre (magn.:x3300)

Fig. 5: Fracture surface of a carbon fibre (magn.:x 3000)

2) G_{IC} of the carbon and glass prepreg is comparable with G_{IC} of the adhesive while G_{IIc} of both prepreps is considerably lower than G_{IIc} of the adhesive.

3) For all intermediate layers tested, G_{IC} is considerably lower than G_{IIc} , the difference being most explicit for the adhesive.

The WTDCB-specimen was also used to examine the influence of mode I fatigue loading on delamination propagation. It was demonstrated that, for an aramid prepreg, delamination propagation can occur at fatigue load levels ($R=0$, $R=P_{\min}/P_{\max}$) significantly below P_{Cr} ($P_{Cr} = (G_{IC}/Q)^{1/2}$). The results are summarized in table 1.

TABLE 1

Delamination growth rate of an aramid prepreg as result of mode I fatigue loading (WTDCB-specimen)

R=0, f=0.1 Hz, constant amplitude loading		
$P_{\max} =$	P_{Cr}	da/dn = infinite (unstable delamination growth)
	0.75 P_{Cr}	= 190 10^{-4} mm/cycle
	0.62 P_{Cr}	= 20 10^{-4} mm/cycle
	0.50 P_{Cr}	= zero (no delamination growth)

Also the adhesive (no fibres embedded) showed delamination growth as the result of mode I fatigue loading (table 2):

TABLE 2

Delamination growth rate of an adhesive as result of mode I fatigue loading (WTDCB-specimen)

R=0, f=0.1 Hz, constant amplitude loading		
$P_{\max} =$	P_{Cr}	da/dn = infinite (unstable delamination growth)
	0.83 P_{Cr}	= 470 10^{-4} mm/cycle
	0.67 P_{Cr}	= 30 10^{-4} mm/cycle
	0.50 P_{Cr}	= 7 10^{-4} mm/cycle
	0.33 P_{Cr}	= zero (no delamination growth)

No fatigue tests have been performed on glass and carbon prepreps.

3: DAMAGE TOLERANCE EVALUATION

In chapter 2 of this paper, the interlaminar fracture toughness of an aramid prepreg was, for both a mode I (peel) and a mode II (shear) type of loading, compared with the interlaminar fracture toughness of a glass and carbon prepreg. It was argued that the lower G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values of the aramid prepreg were probably due to the relatively poor fibre/matrix adhesion.

In chapter 3, the effect of interlaminar fracture toughness (in combination with fibre and matrix properties) on the damage tolerance properties will be

examined. First in section 3.1 some general trends are presented concerning the influence of the matrix and fibre/matrix adhesion on the composite damage tolerance. In section 3.2, laminate models are introduced to present a qualitative evaluation of the damage tolerance behaviour of composites.

3.1: Influence of the matrix and fibre/matrix adhesion on composite damage tolerance

The principal role of the matrix in a composite material is to effect the load transfer between fibres by means of a shear deformation. This function can be performed by a brittle material. However, this first generation of composites had very poor damage tolerance (fracture toughness) properties. Damage tolerance could be improved using different methods:

1) increase of the elastic energy storage capacity of the fibres

However, it should be clear that in this case elastic energy is stored in the fibres; the energy will be released at fracture and therefore no energy is dissipated.

2) introduction of energy dissipating "secondary" fracture mechanisms

The term "secondary" implies that first a "primary" fracture mechanism must have been taken place before this mechanism can be initiated. The best example of a "secondary" mechanism is fibre pull-out in which fracture energy is dissipated as heat (result of friction). This mechanism can only occur after fibre failure and local fibre/matrix debonding.

3) increase of the energy dissipating through plastic deformation of the matrix

The influence of the matrix on method 2 and 3 will be discussed further on. At the moment, a large variety of matrix systems does exist. In fig.6 (from ref. 2, 3, 4), some typical G_{IC} -values are presented for different groups of matrix systems. Where available, in the same figure G_{IC} -values are also shown of carbon composites made of these matrix systems.

Fig. 6: Survey of G_{IC} of different matrix systems (carbon prepregs)

In general, the following remarks can be made concerning the possible improvements on composite damage tolerance by means of matrix upgrading.

1) An improvement of the linear elastic properties of a (brittle) matrix will have a limited effect on composite fracture toughness. A possible benefit is a delayed crack initiation in the matrix itself.

2) Energy dissipation through plastic deformation of the matrix is a well-known method to improve the fracture toughness of a composite. However, fig.6 already showed that the toughness gain of the composite might be much smaller than expected from the improved matrix toughness. This phenomenon can be explained by fibre/matrix interactions:

- fibre stiffness will limit the deformation potential of the matrix
- fibre failure and/or fibre/matrix debonding might occur before the full energy dissipating capacity of the matrix is reached

Although plastic energy dissipation of the matrix is always beneficial, its influence on composite damage tolerance should, because of the relatively low plastic energy capacity of the matrix, not be

overestimated. High impact energies will not be entirely dissipated by matrix plastic deformation but the latter mechanism can lower the impact energy to such an extent that elastic energy storage by the fibres is possible. A similar explanation is valid for fracture mechanisms whereby a lot of energy is released at fracture (e.g. fibre failure).

3) For toughened matrix systems, an increased strength, stiffness and failure strain will be beneficial for the composite fracture toughness. Especially in cases where fibre/matrix interactions can occur, it is important to have significant plastic energy dissipation at a relatively small strain level.

With respect to fibre/matrix adhesion, an optimum adhesion level will significantly improve the composite fracture toughness. However, the optimum is not necessarily the maximum adhesion level, as such it is interesting to examine the consequences of increased fibre/matrix adhesion:

1) More elastic energy can be stored at the interface. However, compared with the energy stored by the fibres, the elastic energy storage will be small and, since the stored energy is released at fracture, a higher energy storage does not have to result in improved damage tolerance.

2) An increase in fibre/matrix adhesion will result in delayed debonding which, for toughened matrices, can result in an improved use of the energy dissipating capacity of the matrix (more opportunity for plastic deformation of the matrix).

3) Improved adhesion can cause fibre failure to occur prior to fibre/matrix debonding. Since debonding mostly results in a more uniform energy distribution in the fibres (fracture energy of a neighboring fibre is stored in a longer length of fibre) this benefit can be lost with improved adhesion and can result in a far less damage tolerant material.

4) Improved adhesion can eliminate "secondary" fracture mechanisms. If fibre failure occurs without fibre/matrix debonding, no fibre pull-out can take place which again can result in significantly less damage tolerance (see section 3.2).

It should be clear that the optimum fibre/matrix adhesion will be strongly dependent on the matrix and fibre properties, e.g. tough matrix systems should have higher fibre/matrix adhesion levels than brittle ones and fibres with a small Weibull modulus should have lower fibre/matrix adhesion levels than fibres with a large Weibull modulus.

3.2: Damage tolerance of composites

In chapter 2, experimental results have been presented on the interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC} , G_{IIC}) of a glass, carbon and aramid prepreg. It was demonstrated that fibre/matrix adhesion significantly influences both fracture toughness parameters. In section 3.1, the possible effects of the matrix and fibre/matrix debonding on composite damage tolerance have been briefly reviewed. In this section, model laminates are introduced to compare the damage tolerance properties of a carbon, glass and aramid laminate. In that respect, attention will be focussed on fibre properties and fibre/matrix adhesion levels. To enable direct comparison between the laminates, an identical matrix system and fibre volume content is assumed for the different fibre types. The fibre and matrix properties used in the qualitative evaluation are presented in fig.7.

Fig. 7: Stress-strain curves of the materials used in the damage tolerance evaluation

Four different cases will be treated:

- tension loaded laminate with an artificial crack
- compression loaded laminate with an artificial delamination
- fatigue loaded laminate with artificial damage
- impact of a laminate

3.2.1: tensile loaded laminate with an artificial crack

The most straightforward example is a laminate consisting of 0° plies with a central through crack. When the external load increases, at the through crack a significant stress transfer will occur from the cut fibre layers to the undisturbed fibre region. The high shear stresses will cause rapid delamination (in length direction). According to the experimental results (fig.3), the aramid laminate will first show the longitudinal splits (delaminations) since

since fibre/matrix debonding can occur at relatively low stress (energy) levels. However, the shear stress peaks are such that the carbon and glass laminates will also show longitudinal delaminations. These longitudinal splits, which will rapidly grow along the total length of the specimen (shear stress peaks follow the moving split tip), largely decrease the stress peaks in the undisturbed fibre region. When the splits reach the specimen ends, the stress peaks are reduced to zero. During the splitting process, fracture energy can be dissipated due to plastic deformation of the matrix (if a tough matrix is used). In this respect, slightly higher energy dissipation can be expected for the carbon and the glass laminate. When the splits have removed the stress concentration, fibre strength will dominate the failure load of the laminate. In that case, aramid HM, S-glass and carbon HT laminates will show comparable results, with a small preference for S-glass which will allow more plastic energy dissipation by the matrix (higher failure strain, see fig.7).

When other ply orientations are introduced, the situation rapidly becomes more complex since besides the orientation also the stacking order will be important. However, in general, the damage tolerance of a laminate will be improved if the stress concentration in the load carrying plies (0°) is decreased. When $\pm 45^\circ$ plies are introduced, stress transfer from the cut fibre layers to the undisturbed fibre region will occur primarily through these $\pm 45^\circ$

plies which causes:

- much lower shear stresses in the 0° plies
- high interply shear stresses between the 0° and the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies

For this type of laminates, aramid fibres are expected to be superior to carbon and glass fibres because:

- The energy storage capacity of aramid (and S-glass) exceeds the capacity of carbon fibres substantially. This means that because of rapid local fibre failure (as a result of stress concentrations) the fracture energy can be stored much better by aramid fibers and will therefore not directly result in catastrophic failure.

- Interply delamination is expected to occur first in the aramid laminate because of its relatively low G_{IIC} value. This delamination will cause a higher shear stress transfer through the 0° plies, will result in longitudinal splitting in these 0° plies and, as a result will decrease local stress concentrations in the 0° plies. For S-glass and carbon laminates this phenomenon will only occur at higher load levels or not at all.

- Because of their high energy storage capacity, aramid fibres may locally fail without causing catastrophic composite failure. If also fibre/matrix debonding does occur at relatively low load levels, fibre pull-out can take place. This "secondary" fracture mechanism can dissipate a significant amount of fracture energy. Again for S-glass and carbon laminates, this pull-out mechanism will appear much later or not at all.

3.2.2: Compression loaded laminate with an artificial delamination

In the case of compressive loading, an (artificial) interply delamination will be considered. It should be clear that the stress-strain curves shown in fig.7 do not apply for compressive loading. With increasing load, severe shear (mode II) and peel (mode I) stresses will appear at the delamination tip. From the experimental results, a delamination extension is expected to

occur first for the aramid laminate. In contrast with tensile loading, the delamination will be disadvantageous for the damage tolerance since it can cause local fibre buckling. Because the peel and shear stresses remain large at the tip of a (growing) delamination, large and rapid delamination extension can be expected which will cause catastrophic failure due to fibre buckling. For laminates with a higher fibre/matrix adhesion level (carbon, glass), delamination extension and catastrophic failure will occur at higher load levels. A similar behaviour will be present if other than 0° plies are applied. Again the aramid laminate will first show delamination extension which finally will result in catastrophic failure.

Remark

Up to now, for both compressive and tensile loading it was assumed that the stress concentration around an artificial damage zone is identical for the different laminates (see one line in $P-G_C$ diagrams). This is not entirely the case. For the unidirectional, in tensile loaded laminates with an artificial crack, a fracture mechanics calculation, developed to predict the stress field around the artificial crack, showed that fibre stiffness is inversely proportional to the shear and peel stress peaks (ref.1). Therefore the lines in the $P-G_C$ diagram should be slightly dissimilar with the highest slope for the glass laminate. However, the general trends, discussed before, will not be affected by this adjustment.

2.2.3: Fatigue loaded laminate with an artificial damage

In chapter 2, some experimental results on fatigue loading were shown (WTDCB-specimen). It was demonstrated that delamination growth can occur at fatigue load levels significantly below the critical fracture load P_{cr} . Although up to now only observed for an aramid prepreg and an adhesive (no fibres embedded), a similar fatigue mechanism can be expected for the carbon and glass prepreg. Because the threshold fatigue load level (for constant amplitude loading and $R=0$, the maximum load level below which no delamination propagation occurs) and delamination growth rates are not known for the different fibre types, a valid comparison is at the moment not possible. The effect of fibre/matrix debonding on the composite damage tolerance will be strongly affected by the sort of fatigue loading present. For tension dominated fatigue loading the debonding can be extremely beneficial because at relatively low load levels "secondary" energy dissipating fracture

mechanisms (fibre pull-out) can take place. For compression dominated fatigue loading the effect of fibre/matrix debonding will be detrimental since it can cause fibre buckling.

3.2.4: Impact of laminates

In the literature the superior impact resistance of aramid laminates has been recognized for quite some time. The main reasons for this superior behaviour have all been introduced in the sections before:

- 1) Aramid exhibits a high (elastic) energy storage capacity.
- 2) Aramid has, compared to S-glass, a relatively high stiffness which results in a rapid stress transfer (impact energy is smeared out over a larger area).
- 3) In aramid laminates, energy can be dissipated by "secondary" fracture mechanisms such as fibre pull-out. These mechanisms are activated at relatively low impact energy levels and can dissipate energy during the total impact event.
- 4) Fibre/matrix debonding in aramid laminates will level off stress concentrations in the fibres. This fracture mechanism postpones fibre failure and therefore possible catastrophic failure.

The beneficial influence of the matrix (plastic energy dissipation) will, for the aramid laminate, be less explicit as compared to glass and carbon laminates but this small disadvantage is largely outweighed by the benefits mentioned before.

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